

ANALYSIS OF THICKNESS-DIRECTION ULTRASONIC WAVE PROPAGATION
OF FIBERGLASS REINFORCED PLASTICS LAMINATES*

Isao Kimpara**, Mitsuo Takehana*** and Toshio Suzuki****

Department of Naval Architecture
The University of Tokyo
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku
Tokyo, 113 Japan

Abstract

The wave-form of a thickness-direction ultrasonic pulse-echo of fiber-glass reinforced plastics (FRP) laminates is generally very complicated due to the effects of inhomogeneous constitutions of glass reinforcements and high internal attenuation of ultrasonic wave in the material. It is often rather difficult to distinguish a necessary base-echo pulse. In this paper the effects of inhomogeneous laminate constitutions and three dimensional effective elastic constants on thickness-direction ultrasonic wave propagation properties of FRP laminates were discussed both theoretically and experimentally. It was shown that intermediate reflected waves in FRP can be removed electrically by applying a suitable level of rejection in order to ensure the detection of a base-echo.

An ultrasonic digital caliper was devised and built as a trial with which thickness of FRP with complex internal constitution can be measured. FRP laminates were fabricated by changing thickness and glass constitution systematically to check the applicability of the trial instrument. The thickness-direction velocity and attenuation constant of ultrasonic waves in these laminates were evaluated on the trial instrument as functions of laminate constitutions and fiber volume fractions. It was confirmed that the accuracy ± 5 % can be attained in the ultrasonic thickness measurements of FRP laminates of 3 - 30 mm in thickness.

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** Associate Professor, Dr.

*** Professor, Dr.

**** Assistant

Introduction

Fiberglass reinforced plastics (FRP) are being utilized in progressively increasing amount for structural applications with increasing demand on structural integrity. In manufacturing FRP products, their structural materials and most of structural forms are made in a single process of molding , so that the various material inspections must be performed on the completed products. Among the many check items of FRP products, the measurement of thickness is the most basic one. Although the glass content of FRP is also another one of the basic items, it can be roughly estimated by measuring the thickness with knowledge of fabrication method and reinforcement type used. Thus, the thickness of a FRP laminate is the first variable that must be measured when a laminate is to be judged. When measuring the thickness of a FRP laminate with existing ultrasonic type or electromagnetic type instruments, however, stabilized numerical values can not be gained and there is no repeatability. In addition, complex steps are often needed when measuring.

Considering the state of art, the Japan Craft Inspection Organization (JCI) set up the "FRP Non-destructive Inspection Committee" in 1975 in order to establish an effective non-destructive method for measuring the thickness and detecting the internal structure of a FRP laminate in the inspection or manufacturing field of FRP ships (1). As a result of studying existing instruments, it was concluded that ultrasonic type instruments are most suitable for measuring the thickness of FRP and it was decided to improve this type of instrument. Being requested to do the experiment and analysis in this study by JCI, the authors performed fundamental experiments on the thickness-direction ultrasonic wave propagation properties on a trial instrument to check the accuracy of ultrasonic thickness measurements of FRP laminates with various glass constitutions. The results from this study are described below.

Preliminary Considerations

FRP used in hand laid-up laminates are generally composed of woven rovings (R) and chopped strand mats (M) as reinforcements and unsaturated polyester resin as a matrix. Their laminate constitutions are expressed by the combination of M and R such as (MR)x2 + M, (MRM)x3, etc. This type of FRP has a medium glass content: $W_f = 25 - 50\%$ in fiber weight fraction. The following simplified calculation were performed to evaluate the thickness-direction ultrasonic wave propagation properties in such type of FRP.

Effective Elastic Constants of Bidirectional Laminates

In order to get a measure of laminate thickness from the transmission of a thickness-direction pressure wave, the velocity of the wave has to be known. Consequently it is necessary to estimate the longitudinal wave velocity normal to fibers. For this purpose, the three dimensional effective elastic constants of a laminate can be evaluated based on those of a unidirectional layer as described below.

Assuming transversely isotropy, the generalized Hooke's law of a unidirectional layer gives in the principal directions :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{12} \\ c_{12} & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ c_{12} & c_{23} & c_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where x is the fiber direction (L), y and z are taken in the transverse plane normal to fibers (T).

The elastic stiffnesses, c_{ij} , are expressed in terms of the principal elastic constants ; Young's moduli, E_L , E_T , and Poisson's ratios, ν_{LT} , ν_{TL} and ν_{TT} , as follows :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} c_{11} &= (1 - \nu_{TT}^2)E_L / \Delta \\ c_{12} &= \nu_{LT}(1 + \nu_{TT})E_T / \Delta = \nu_{TL}(1 + \nu_{TT})E_L / \Delta \\ c_{22} &= (1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})E_T / \Delta \\ c_{23} &= (\nu_{TT} + \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})E_T / \Delta \\ \Delta &= 1 - \nu_{TT}^2 - 2\nu_{LT}\nu_{TL} - 2\nu_{LT}\nu_{TT}\nu_{TL} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

A unidirectional composite was idealized into regularly-spaced square or hexagonal array models of circular inclusions in a matrix. The basic segment in these regularly-arranged transverse models were analyzed by a finite element method (FEM) under a generalized plane strain (2, 3). The fiber volume fraction of the basic segment was varied from 10 to 70 % at an interval of 10 % to obtain the relations between the principal elastic constants and the fiber volume fraction. The nominal values used in the FEM calculations are as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Young's moduli} & ; E_f = 7400 \text{ kgf/mm}^2, E_m = 350 \text{ kgf/mm}^2 \\ \text{Poisson's ratios} & ; \nu_f = 0.23, \nu_m = 0.36 \end{aligned}$$

where the subscripts f and m indicate fiber (glass fiber) and matrix (unsaturated polyester resin), respectively.

MR-type laminates are typical bidirectional ones, which are idealized into a cross-plyed laminate consisting of unidirectional layers as shown in Fig.1. The gross stresses and strains of the laminate are expressed as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{mean stresses} & ; \sigma_x = (1/2)\{\sigma_x^{(1)} + \sigma_x^{(2)}\}, \sigma_y = (1/2)\{\sigma_y^{(1)} + \sigma_y^{(2)}\}, \\ & \sigma_z = \sigma_z^{(1)} = \sigma_z^{(2)} \\ \text{mean strains} & ; \epsilon_x = \epsilon_x^{(1)} = \epsilon_x^{(2)}, \epsilon_y = \epsilon_y^{(1)} = \epsilon_y^{(2)}, \\ & \epsilon_z = (1/2)\{\epsilon_z^{(1)} + \epsilon_z^{(2)}\} \end{aligned}$$

where $\sigma_x^{(i)}, \sigma_y^{(i)}, \sigma_z^{(i)}; \epsilon_x^{(i)}, \epsilon_y^{(i)}, \epsilon_z^{(i)}$ ($i= 1, 2$) are the stresses and strains in each layer.

Fig.1 - Bidirectional laminate model.

Hence the Hooke's law of the cross-plyed laminate is given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_z \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{c}_{11} & \bar{c}_{12} & \bar{c}_{13} \\ \bar{c}_{12} & \bar{c}_{11} & \bar{c}_{13} \\ \bar{c}_{13} & \bar{c}_{13} & \bar{c}_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_z \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where the effective stiffnesses of the laminate are expressed as follows :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \bar{c}_{11} &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ c_{11} + c_{22} - \frac{(c_{23} - c_{12})^2}{2c_{22}} \right\} \\ \bar{c}_{12} &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ 2c_{12} + \frac{(c_{23} - c_{12})^2}{2c_{22}} \right\} \\ \bar{c}_{13} &= \frac{1}{2} (c_{12} + c_{23}) \\ \bar{c}_{33} &= c_{22} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

As the cross-plyed laminate is regarded as in-plane tetragonal syngony plate, the principal elastic constants become with $x, y \rightarrow 1, z \rightarrow 2$

$$E_x = E_y = E_1, E_z = E_2; \nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx} = \nu_{11}, \nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz} = \nu_{12}, \nu_{zx} = \nu_{zy} = \nu_{21}$$

which are expressed in terms of the effective stiffnesses as follows :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_1 &= \bar{\nu} / (\bar{c}_{11}\bar{c}_{33} - \bar{c}_{13}^2) \\ E_2 &= \bar{\nu} / (\bar{c}_{11}^2 - \bar{c}_{12}^2) \\ \nu_{11} &= (\bar{c}_{12}\bar{c}_{33} - \bar{c}_{13}^2) / (\bar{c}_{11}\bar{c}_{33} - \bar{c}_{13}^2) \\ \nu_{12} &= (\bar{c}_{11}\bar{c}_{13} - \bar{c}_{12}\bar{c}_{13}) / (\bar{c}_{11}\bar{c}_{33} - \bar{c}_{13}^2) \\ \nu_{21} &= (\bar{c}_{11}\bar{c}_{13} - \bar{c}_{12}\bar{c}_{13}) / (\bar{c}_{11}^2 - \bar{c}_{12}^2) \\ \bar{\nu} &= \bar{c}_{11}^2\bar{c}_{33} + 2\bar{c}_{12}\bar{c}_{13}^2 - 2\bar{c}_{11}\bar{c}_{13}^2 - \bar{c}_{12}^2\bar{c}_{33} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Then the thickness-direction longitudinal wave velocity in an orthotropic plate is given by

$$c_z = \sqrt{\bar{c}_{33} / \rho} \quad (6)$$

In the case of bidirectional laminate as shown in Fig.1, the above equation gives

$$c_2 = \frac{\sqrt{E_2/\rho} \sqrt{(1 - \nu_{11}) / (1 - \nu_{11} - 2\nu_{12}\nu_{21})}}{\quad} \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the density which is given by the law of mixture :

$$\rho = \rho_f \nu_f + \rho_m (1 - \nu_f) \quad (8)$$

in which the nominal values are used for $\rho_f = 2.60 \text{ gr/cm}^3$ (glass fiber), $\rho_m = 1.20 \text{ gr/cm}^3$ (cured polyester resin).

Figure 2 shows the relation between calculated values of thickness-direction Young's modulus and fiber volume fraction. It should be noted that

E_2 is greater than E_T due to the so-called bonding effect. E_2 is calculated based on the square array model. Although the square array model gives a higher estimation of E_T than the hexagonal one, the discrepancy between both is not great within medium fiber content range as shown in Fig.2. The simplified E_T model as shown in Fig.2 is an approximation of square array model, which gives a simple closed-form formula :

$$E_T = \frac{E_m \{ \sqrt{V_f} E_f + (1 - \sqrt{V_f}) E_m \}}{(1 - \sqrt{V_f}) \{ \sqrt{V_f} E_f + (1 - \sqrt{V_f}) E_m \} + \sqrt{V_f} E_m} \quad (9)$$

It can be seen that the above equation is a good approximation within medium fiber content range (2).

Figure 3 shows the relation between Poisson's ratio and fiber volume fraction in the bidirectional laminate based on the square array model. It is interesting to note that the second term related to Poisson's ratios in the right hand side of Equation (7), which is here referred to as "Poisson factor", does not change greatly with fiber content within medium fiber fraction range.

In both figures, the abscissa is shown for fiber volume and weight fractions, V_f and W_f . The relation between both is given by

$$V_f = \frac{W_f \rho_m}{W_f (\rho_m - \rho_f) + \rho_f} \quad (10)$$

Fig.2 - Thickness-direction Young's modulus versus fiber volume fraction.

Fig.3 - Poisson's ratio versus fiber volume fraction.

Pulse Propagation Normal to Laminates

The main difficulties in applying the ultrasonic pulse-echo technique to FRP laminates, compared to metals, are due to the high internal attenuation of ultrasonic wave and their inhomogeneity. The reinforcement, when concentrated in layers, particularly of woven roving, will scatter and reflect the incident wave and thus obscure the base-echo by generating an intermediate echo. The effect of inhomogeneity is discussed below on the simplest type of one dimensional wave propagation.

When two materials share a common plane boundary as shown in Fig.4, the conditions of stress and particle velocity give (4)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_T &= \frac{2\rho_2c_2}{\rho_1c_1 + \rho_2c_2} \\ \sigma_R &= \frac{\rho_2c_2 - \rho_1c_1}{\rho_1c_1 + \rho_2c_2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

where σ_I is the incident wave, σ_T is the transmitted wave, σ_R is the reflected wave and $\rho_i c_i$ ($i=1, 2$) is the acoustic impedance of each material.

Fig.4 - Transmission and reflection at an interface.

Defining by

$$K = \rho_2c_2 / \rho_1c_1 \quad (12)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_T &= \{2/(\kappa + 1)\} \sigma_I \\ \sigma_R &= \{(\kappa - 1)/(\kappa + 1)\} \sigma_I \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

Consider a n-plyed laminate composed of alternating layers of two homogeneous isotropic elastic materials under a step pulse of magnitude σ_0 at $N=0$, as shown in Fig.5. Then following Kinslow's method (5), we have

Primary intermediate-echo :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_i &= \{(1 - \kappa)/2\} \{2/(1 + \kappa)\}^{2i-1} \sigma_0 && \text{if } i \text{ even} \\ \sigma_i &= \{(\kappa - 1)/2\} \{2/(1 + \kappa)\}^{2i-1} \kappa^{i-1} \sigma_0 && \text{if } i \text{ odd} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

Primary base-echo (n odd) :

$$\sigma_b = \{(\kappa + 1)/2\} \{2/(1 + \kappa)\}^{2n-1} \kappa^{n-1} \sigma_0 \quad (15)$$

In the case of MR-type laminates, the thickness-direction acoustic impedance is estimated for M and R layers by calculating the wave velocity as described above.

For M layer ($W_F = 30\%$) ; $\rho_M c_M = 0.321 \times 10^6 \text{ gr/cm}^2/\text{s}$

For R layer ($W_F = 50\%$) ; $\rho_R c_R = 0.389 \times 10^6 \text{ gr/cm}^2/\text{s}$

which give

$$\kappa_{MR} \text{ (M to R) } = 1.21 \quad ; \quad \sigma_R/\sigma_I = 0.095$$

$$\kappa_{RM} \text{ (R to M) } = 0.824 \quad ; \quad \sigma_R/\sigma_I = -0.096$$

The actual stress experienced by a particular laminate depends, of course, on the profile of the incident pulse as well as its magnitude. Figure 6 shows an example of observed ultrasonic reflected wave-form in a MR-type laminate (6). As seen in the figure, the intermediate-echo can be distinguished, which supports the above qualitative explanation. One of the authors had previously reported that the internal structure of MR-type laminates can be detected by ultrasonic (6). The intermediate-echo, particularly when woven roving is used, may be of the same order of magnitude as the base-echo as shown in Fig.6.

Fig.5 - Laminate composed of alternating layers of two homogeneous materials.

Fig.6 - Ultrasonic reflected wave-form of a MR-type laminate (10 MHz, AC).

Materials

The constitutions and the designed values of FRP test laminates are shown in Table I.

Table I - Constitutions and designed values of FRP test laminates.

Molding Method	Symbol	Glass Constitution	Thickness (mm)	Glass Content (wt%)
Spray-up	S-1		3	25
	2	Random	5	"
	3	Chopped	7	"
	4	Roving	9	"
	5		12	"
	6		15	"
Hand lay-up	H1-1	M x 3	3	30
	2	5	5	"
	3	7	7	"
	4	9	9	"
	5	12	12	"
	6	15	15	"
	H2-1	R x 3	3	50
	2	5	5	"
	3	7	7	"
	4	9	9	"
	5	12	12	"
	6	15	15	"
Hand lay-up	H3-1	(MR x 1) + M	3	38
	2	(" 2)	5	40
	3	(" 3)	7	41
	4	(" 4)	9	42
	5	(" 5)	12	"
	6	(" 6)	15	"
Hand lay-up	H4-1	MRM x 1	3	38
	2	MR'M x 2	5	36
	3	" x 3	7	"
	4	MRM x 3	9	38
	5	" 4	12	"
	6	" 5	15	"

The glass reinforcements, the matrix resin and the molding conditions used are as follows :

Glass reinforcements ;

for spray-up, chopped roving ER-2310 (produced by Unitika Co., Ltd.)

for hand lay-up, chopped strand mat (symbol M) 450 gr/m²

MC 450A (produced by Nittobo Co., Ltd.)

woven roving (symbol R) 860 gr/m²

WR 860-100 (same as above)

woven roving (symbol R') 570 gr/m²

WR 570-100 (same as above)

Matrix resin ; unsaturated polyester resin Rigolac 158 BQT (produced by Showa Kobunshi Co., Ltd.)

Hardener ; methylethylketonperoxide (MEKPO)

externally blended type (for spray-up), 1.0 wt% (for hand lay-up)

Molding conditions ; temperature 24 - 25°C, humidity 65 %RH, after cure 80°C x 5 hour

Neglecting the internal porosity, the glass content can be calculated from the thickness. Figure 7 shows the comparison between calculated and measured glass content of the test specimens. Both appear to be in good accordance with the designed values.

Fig.7 - Glass content versus thickness of test specimens.

Experiments

An ultrasonic digital caliper was devised and built as a trial with which the thickness of FRP laminates with complex internal structure can be measured from one side only. Fundamental experiments were performed on the trial instrument with the test laminates.

Ultrasonic Digital Caliper for FRP Laminates

For years the thickness of metal plates has been successfully measured by the ultrasonic pulse-echo technique. When applied to FRP laminates, however, the instrument normally used for metals did not work well. So it was decided to develop an ultrasonic digital caliper suitable for FRP laminates.

In the case of FRP laminates, the reflected ultrasonic waves appear in a complicated form due to the intermediate echoes by reinforcement layers as described above. It is often difficult to distinguish between base-echo pulse, flaw pulse and reinforcement-echo pulse, etc. Especially at higher frequencies, it is still harder to distinguish the base-echo in a complicated reflected waveform.

By lowering frequency range to 0.5 - 1.0 MHz and applying a rejection circuit, the waveform on only a base-echo pulse and a flaw pulse can be observed. Rejection is attained by adjusting the input sensitivity level of ultrasonic waves which reflect in a complex way and has effect of letting reflected waves over a certain established level pass. The input level of a trial instrument is changeable so that rejection can be adjusted.

A trial instrument was produced by Nihon Dempa Kogyo Co., Ltd. which was called "FRP Thickness Counter Model ZM-102". Figure 8 shows a view of the trial instrument. A schema of the measuring principle is shown in Fig.9. The principal capacity of the trial instrument is as follows :

- | | |
|-----------------------|--|
| 1. Measuring range | ; 3 - 45 mm |
| 2. Measuring accuracy | ; Total $\pm 5\%$ (Accuracy of the instrument is ± 0.1 mm.) |
| 3. Indication | ; Displayed in LED 4 digits on Braun tube screen |
| 4. Applied frequency | ; 0.5 MHz or 1.0 MHz |
| 5. Measuring method | ; Ultrasonic pulse-echo type with sending/receiving ultrasonic probe |

Fig.8 - FRP thickness counter built as a trial.

Thickness-direction Velocity of Sound

When an ultrasonic pulse signal is transmitted into a FRP laminate by making water the contact medium and bonding a probe onto the surface of a laminate, it is reflected from the bottom. By indicating its waveform on a Braun tube screen and reading the time lag between the penetrating point T and the rising point of the base-echo B, the thickness-direction velocity of sound in FRP is calculated by the following equation :

$$c = 2l/t \tag{16}$$

where c is the velocity of sound, l is the thickness of a laminate and t is the time lag between T and B indicated on a Braun tube screen.

Figure 11 shows the block diagram of the experiment to measure the velocity of sound. The saw-tooth waves above the ultrasonic reflected waves, as shown in Fig.10, are to calibrate the time axis. A signal is sent directly into the oscilloscope from a frequency oscillator in order to measure the velocity of sound precisely. The velocity of sound in FRP is affected by the glass constitution and the glass content. There is a tendency that it is low when the glass content is low and it increases as the glass content increases. It has been found to range from about 2200 m/s to 3200 m/s. When using ordinary steel material and measuring with the same instrument, the velocity of sound in steel was between 5600 m/s and 6200 m/s, which is about in accordance with the nominal value of 5800 m/s to 6000 m/s (1.0 MHz, ultrasonic flaw detection).

Figure 12 shows the comparison between calculated and observed velocity of sound in the test laminates. The solid curves in the figure were calculated based on the results as described above. The measured mean values of

Fig.10 - Examples of reflected ultrasonic waves on a Braun tube screen.

Fig.11 - Block diagram of experiment to measure velocity of sound.

Fig.12 - Thickness-direction velocity of sound versus fiber volume fraction.

velocity of sound appear to be in good accordance with the theoretical curve except H2 laminate without rejection. This error may probably due to the rough surface of woven roving laminates.

It should be noted that the velocity of sound apparently decreases with rejection, since the base-echo B moves backward with the rising portion of base-echo pulse eliminated by rejection, as can be seen in Fig.10. It may also noted that the rejection tends to average the difference of velocity of sound due to glass constitutions. Det Norske Veritas uses a nominal velocity of sound of 2520 m/s for FRP laminate inspection (7), which may be supported by the above results. Thus the experiment suggested that 3 channels of velocity of sound, 2400 m/s to 2600 m/s, might cover the whole range for FRP laminates.

Ultrasonic Attenuation Constants

Considerable part of ultrasonic attenuation might be absorption in FRP laminates, since plastics in general absorb much more sound than metals. By holding the sensitivity and other items of the instrument unchanged and reading the base-echo height for laminates of different thickness on a Broun tube screen, the thickness-direction ultrasonic attenuation constant is calculated by the following equation :

$$\alpha = [10/(l_x - l_o)] \log(P_x/P_o) \tag{17}$$

where α is the attenuation constant, l_o is the standard thickness, l_x is another thickness, P_o and P_x are the base-echo height for the thickness l_o and l_x , respectively.

Fig.13 - Ultrasonic attenuation constant versus fiber volume fraction.

Figure 13 shows the measured mean values thus obtained. It is shown that the attenuation constant depends more greatly on the glass constitution than on the glass content : the attenuation is rather small for comparatively homogeneous laminates such as spray (S), mat (H1) and woven roving (H2), while it becomes large for inhomogeneous mixed laminates such as MR-type (H3) and MRM-type (H4). It is also noted that the attenuation of 0.5 MHz is roughly two times as large as that of 1.0 MHz.

Accuracy of Ultrasonic Thickness Measurements

The accuracy of the trial instrument was checked by ultrasonic thickness measurements on various types of FRP laminates. The probe was put on the surface of a test specimen with water as the contact medium and the base-echo was confirmed by adjusting the rejection and the sensitivity. Then, the height of base-echo was fixed to be 80 - 90 % on the Braun tube screen by fine adjustment of the sensitivity. In a series measurement for each type of laminates, the calibration was made on a specimen of a certain known thickness by adjustment of the velocity-of-sound dial so that the digital indicator showed the true thickness.

Figure 14 shows the deviations between measured values by the caliper and true ones for each type of laminates. It is shown that the accuracy of the trial ultrasonic caliper is roughly within the prescribed limit of ± 5 %. Frequencies of 0.5 and 1.0 MHz were used for these measurements. Suitable frequency of 1.0 MHz was used for thinner plates of about 3 - 8 mm and 0.5 MHz for thicker plates of about 5 - 30 mm. According to the test results, it is more suitable to use 0.5 MHz for materials with larger attenuation.

Conclusions

Fundamental studies were performed on the thickness-direction ultrasonic wave propagation properties of FRP laminates. By electrically removing intermediate reflected waves and leaving only the base-echo pulse, an instrument was developed with which the thickness of FRP laminates with complex internal structure can be measured from one side only. With the trial instrument, it was confirmed that the thickness of FRP laminates of 3 - 30 mm in thickness can be measured from one side only by one person with the accuracy of ± 5 % depending upon appropriate selection of rejection level and frequency (0.5 or 1.0 MHz).

As for the measurement of the thickness of inhomogeneous FRP laminates, the results as expected were achieved. The trial instrument used in the experiments was tested also in the field and improved into a lighter, smaller and portable type after changing some specifications based on the test results (see Appendix). As for the inspection of internal structure of FRP including detection of glass constitution and internal defects, there are good prospects of developing a suitable practical system based on the achieved results.

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Fig.14 - Accuracy of ultrasonic thickness measurements for FRP laminates.

Nomenclature

σ	=	normal stress
ϵ	=	normal strain
c_{ij}	=	elastic stiffness of unidirectional layer
\bar{c}_{ij}	=	effective stiffness of bidirectional laminate
E	=	Young's modulus
ν	=	Poisson's ratio
c	=	longitudinal wave velocity (velocity of sound)
ρ	=	density
ρc	=	acoustic impedance
V_f	=	fiber volume fraction
W_f	=	fiber weight fraction
α	=	attenuation constant
t	=	time lag
l	=	thickness

Subscripts :

x, y, z	;	principal directions of orthotropic plate (x, y ; in-plane, z ; thickness-direction)
$1, 2$;	principal directions of in-plane tetragonal syngony plate (1 ; in-plane, 2 ; thickness-direction)
L	;	longitudinal (parallel to fiber)
T	;	transverse (perpendicular to fiber)
f	;	fiber
m	;	matrix

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Appendix

The trial instrument ZM-102 used in the experiments was remodeled into a lighter, smaller and portable type for practical field use by Nihon Dempa Kogyo Co., Ltd., which was called "FRP Ultrasonic Caliper Model UC-800" as shown in Fig.A-1. Some of the specifications of the former model was changed based on the test results. The principal capacity of the new model is as follows :

- | | |
|--------------------------------------|--|
| 1. Measuring range | ; (1) 3 - 15 mm (2) 3 - 30 mm (3) 3 - 60 mm |
| 2. Measurement accuracy | ; Total $\pm 5\%$ (Accuracy of the instrument is ± 0.1 mm) |
| 3. Indication | ; Displayed in LED 3 digits on Braun tube screen |
| 4. Applied frequency | ; 0.5 MHz or 1.0 MHz |
| 5. Measuring method | ; Ultrasonic pulse-echo type with sending/receiving ultrasonic probe |
| 6. Rejection | ; Fixed |
| 7. Set-up range of velocity of sound | ; 2400, 2500 and 2600 m/s
3 channel |
| 8. Size of Braun tube | ; Square Braun tube of 18 x 27 mm
(with a magnifier) |
| 9. Power source | ; DC 6 V battery (for charging) |
| 10. Ambient temperature | ; -5°C - $+45^{\circ}\text{C}$ |
| 11. Weight | ; About 4.0 kg |

Fig.A-1 - FRP Ultrasonic Caliper Model UC-800.